
Deliverable D-JIP2-4.2.2

Workpackage JIP2-WP4 Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners: IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI

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GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	Deliverable D-JIP2-4.2.2 FoodChain-Lab with integrated network analysis module as a web-service, browser-ready, open source and implemented in the BfR cloud
WP and Task	JIP-WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control; T2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework ST2: Programming a software and developing an algorithm
Leader	BfR
Other contributors	IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI
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FOODCHAIN-LAB WITH INTEGRATED NETWORK ANALYSIS MODULE AS A WEB-SERVICE, BROWSER-READY, OPEN SOURCE AND IMPLEMENTED IN THE BFR CLOUD

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As an integrative project, EJP COHESIVE aims at unifying the efforts of different WPs/tasks within COHESIVE as well as of different national and international projects and across multiple disciplines. The FoodChain-Lab Web application (FCL Web) as modular tracing platform is an example for this. The actual development of new features and functions is done in other projects such as the EFSA-BfR cooperation or the cooperation with the German Federal State North Rhine-Westphalia. However, integrating those functions into FCL Web and developing the infrastructure for the FCL Web application (e.g. user management, databases, user server) also needs a lot work. This is done as integrative task within COHESIVE. In the end, FCL Web is a result of several projects which is allowing FCL Web to advance faster to be available for a broad range of users in Europe earlier.

In COHESIVE subtask 4.2.2 it was the aim to unify several modules for data collection, cleaning, visualisation and reporting – in part developed in the framework of other projects - in one platform:

- A data collection module
- An interactive analysis module
- A WGS-data integration module
- A reporting module
- A synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab

This subtask was mainly a software programming and algorithm developing task. The deliverable of this subtask is the integrative ready-to-use, free and open source tracing web portal FCL Web which is accessible at <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>.

The interactive analysis module of FCL Web including the algorithm to analyze delivery networks was developed in the framework of a cooperation project with EFSA and is now integrated in the tracing portal. For each food business operator and for each product in the delivery network a score is calculated to give an instant visual feedback on e.g. which food business operator could be the potential common source of a contamination. It is possible to run simulations on cross contamination or inactivation of a contamination as well.

A reporting module – the Rapid Outbreak Assessment (ROA) style – was developed during the EFSA implemented and integrated in the tracing web portal. The ROA style visualises tracing, sample and case information in a format which is suitable for publishing the results of tracing analyses in outbreak reports such as the EFSA-ECDC Joint Rapid Outbreak Assessments just in one click. For this, a JSON-based data exchange module was developed to import delivery data obtained from EFSA.

A synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab (FCL) based on a JSON file exchange module was integrated as well to be able to make use of the advantages of both the web and the desktop FCL.

An online data collection mask for tracing data was developed in the framework of a national project together with the German federal state North Rhine-Westphalia. The mask is available in multiple languages: German, English, Italian and Norwegian. As soon as this data collection mask is publically available, it will be integrated into FCL Web. In addition, a JSON-based data exchange format allows for visualising and analysing delivery data obtained from the data collection mask in FCL Web.

The integration of the WGS-data module is still work in progress. It will be integrated by the end of the COHESIVE project in 2021. The respective deliverable D- JIP2-4.2.3 and milestone M-A2. COHESIVE.4.10 was postponed to M38 and M40.

In addition to the modules listed above which were initially planned to be integrated into FCL Web, more modules from other projects will be integrated in FCL Web soon:

- A prototype of a data cleaning module was developed as a KNIME server workflow
- A prediction module developed in EJP NOVA

During summer 2019, a web-security audit of the tracing web portal was conducted in the framework of the cooperation project with EFSA to ensure secure handling of sensitive information.

FCL Web in its current state was already used in several user trainings as well as in the “Joint EFSA-BfR simulation exercise to strengthen regional networks for crisis preparedness and communication in times of crisis”. FCL Web was also used by EFSA during outbreak investigations and visualisations from FCL Web were published in the RASFF system.